

BIG FIVE FACTORS OF PERSONALITY AMONG PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER-TRAINEES OF PUNJAB IN RELATION TO GENDER

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the Big Five factors of personality among Physical Education teacher-trainees concerning gender differences. A thorough examination of existing literature, coupled with a meta-analysis, revealed inconsistencies in the comparison of Big Five factors across diverse populations concerning gender. Study was delimited to Physical education teacher-trainees studying in colleges and departments of physical education located at Jalandhar, Hoshiarpur and Kapurthala Districts of Punjab. The final sample consisted of 228 (Female=92; Male=136) Physical education teacher-trainees from these districts. Big Five Inventory (BFI) developed by John, Donahue, and Kentle (1991) was used to measure Big Five Factors of Personality of Physical education teacher-trainees. Analysis in relation to t test revealed that male and female Teacher-trainees had equal level of all Factors of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality except Agreeableness and Conscientiousness. Female Teacher-trainees had higher level of Agreeableness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality than male Teacher-trainees. Male Teacher-trainees had higher level of Conscientiousness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality than female Teacher-trainees.

INTRODUCTION

The significance of the Big Five factors extends into the realm of sports psychology and physical education, playing a pivotal role in understanding the psychological dimensions of teaching and learning within this domain. In the context of physical education, the personality of a physical education teacher is a key influence on various facets of a learner's development. This impact is particularly pronounced in traditional, offline teaching settings, where the teacher's personality directly shapes the characteristics of the learners. Moreover, gender, as a social construct, assumes considerable importance in shaping the personality of the physical education teacher trainees and exerting effects on the academic and non-academic aspects of the learners' lives. Consequently, there exists a pressing need to explore and uncover the factors

contributing to the personality of Physical education teacher-trainees, with a specific emphasis on understanding the intricate interplay between these factors and the role of gender in the educational landscape.

Several studies have consistently reported findings on personality traits, with agreeableness and neuroticism exhibiting notable patterns. Costa, Terracciano, and McCrae (2001) observed that women tend to score higher than men in warmth and openness to feelings, while men score higher in assertiveness and openness to ideas. This gender-based distinction is further supported by various studies; for instance, women consistently scored higher on neuroticism and agreeableness (Costa, Terracciano, & McCrae, 2001; Goodwin & Gotlib, 2004; Chapman, Duberstein, & Lyness, 2007; Shokri, Kadivar, & Daneshvarpoor, 2007; Schmitt, Realo, Voracek, & Allik, 2008). Conversely, men tended to score higher on openness to experience, as evidenced by findings from studies conducted by Goodwin and Gotlib (2004) and Shokri, Kadivar, and Daneshvarpoor (2007). In a comprehensive examination, Chapman et al. (2007) reported that across college and adult samples, women consistently scored higher than men in the five-factor model personality traits of neuroticism and agreeableness.

Further supporting these trends, Soudeh and Masoud (2012) highlighted significant differences in the Big Five personality factors between female and male students. Their findings revealed that girls scored significantly higher on openness to experience and agreeableness compared to boys. This growing body of literature underscores the importance of understanding gender-specific patterns in personality traits, providing a valuable foundation for exploring similar dynamics within the context of physical education and sports psychology.

Upon a thorough examination of existing literature concerning the Big Five personality factors, it became evident that research focusing on the population of physical education teacher trainees, particularly in the context of gender differences, is noticeably scarce. Existing studies predominantly centered around university students, and the dearth of investigations specifically targeting physical education teacher trainees in the Indian context was striking. This notable gap in the literature prompted the initiation of the present study.

A comprehensive review of the available literature and a meticulous analysis of meta-analyses underscored notable inconsistencies when comparing Big Five factors based on gender across diverse populations. These inconsistencies, thoroughly expounded upon in the literature review, emphasized the need for further exploration and clarification. Consequently, the present study was conceived to address and contribute to the discourse surrounding these discrepancies. Recognizing the regional context, the research focuses on physical education

teacher trainees in Punjab, India, aiming to provide insights that are not only academically enriching but also culturally relevant and applicable to the local educational landscape.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Big Five Factors of Personality among Physical education teacher-trainees of Punjab in relation to Gender

OBJECTIVES

1. To compare Extraversion Factor of Personality Physical education teacher-trainees in relation to Gender.
2. To compare Agreeableness Factor of Personality Physical education teacher-trainees in relation to Gender.
3. To compare Conscientiousness Factor of Personality Physical education teacher-trainees in relation to Gender.
4. To compare Neuroticism Factor of Personality Physical education teacher-trainees in relation to Gender.
5. To compare Openness to Experience Factor of Personality Physical education teacher-trainees in relation to Gender.

METHODOLOGY

The present study employed a descriptive survey research method to comprehensively investigate and analyse the key variables.

Sample

The population of the present study is defined as all Physical education teacher-trainees studying in colleges and departments of physical education located at Jalandhar, Hoshiarpur and Kapurthala Districts of Punjab. Initially, the data was collected from total 250 teacher-trainees. But later at the time of tabulation it was found that the data of 22 teacher-trainees were not completed. That is why; the data of those 22 teacher-trainees were not taken for the final analysis. Hence, the final sample consisted of 228 (female=92; male=136) Physical education teacher-trainees from these district.

TOOLS

The Big Five Inventory (BFI), developed by John, Donahue, and Kentle (1991), served as the tool for assessing the Big Five Factors of Personality among Physical Education teacher-trainees. This inventory gauges five personality factors: Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, and Openness to Experience. Notably, only the Neuroticism Factor of Personality exhibited a negative orientation, while the remaining four factors were positively framed. Due to the inherent nature of Neuroticism being negative, aggregation of

scores across all factors was not feasible. This inventory consists of 44 statements with five response categories i.e. Disagree strongly, Disagree a little, neither agree nor disagree, Agree a little, and Agree strongly. Results of Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficients were Extraversion .789, Agreeableness .827, Conscientiousness .873, .710 and .701.

DATA COLLECTION

Data collection for the current study involved personal visits conducted by the investigator to institutions within the sampled pool. Following the administration of the tests, both booklets and response sheets were gathered. Subsequently, the scoring process was carried out in adherence to the instructions outlined in the respective manual. The collected data was then subjected to meticulous tabulation and analysis, aligning with the predefined objectives of the study.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 2 Comparison of Extraversion Factor of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	Result
Male	136	28.681	4.1447	.4885	1.765	Not Sig
Female	92	27.506	4.8891	.3914		

In Table 2, the t-value for Gender is reported as 1.765, indicating non-significance at the .05 level. This implies that the mean scores of the Extraversion Factor of Personality, within the broader context of the Big Five Factors of Personality, do not show a significant difference between male and female Teacher-trainees. Accordingly, the "null hypothesis" asserting, "There is no significant difference in Extraversion Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender," is not rejected based on this evidence. In conclusion, it may be inferred that male and female Teacher-trainees exhibit an equal level of the Extraversion Factor of Personality within the framework of the Big Five Factors of Personality.

Table 3 Comparison of Agreeableness Factor of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	Result
Male	136	34.122	4.5228	.3621	3.426	Sig at .05 level
Female	92	36.458	5.3179	.6267		

Table 3 shows the t- value for Gender is 3.426 which is significant at .05 level. It means that mean score of Agreeableness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of

male and female Teacher-trainees differ significantly. On basis of this "null hypothesis" "There is no significant difference in Agreeableness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender" is rejected. Further mean score of Agreeableness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of female is higher than males. It may be concluded that female Teacher-trainees had higher level of Agreeableness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality than male Teacher-trainees.

Table 4 Comparison of Conscientiousness Factor of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	Result
Male	136	33.847	5.2773	.6219	2.347	Sig at .05
Female	92	32.135	5.0495	.4043		

Table 4 shows the t- value for Gender is 2.347 which is significant at .05 level. It means that mean score of Conscientiousness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of male and female Teacher-trainees differ significantly. On basis of this "null hypothesis" "There is no significant difference in Conscientiousness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender" is rejected. Further mean score of Conscientiousness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of males is higher than females. It may be concluded that male Teacher-trainees had higher level of Conscientiousness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality than female Teacher-trainees.

Table 5 Comparison of Neuroticism Factor of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	Result
Male	136	24.417	4.7642	.5615	.479	Not Sig
Female	92	24.756	5.0716	.4061		

In Table 5, the t-value for Gender is reported as .479, indicating non-significance at the .05 level. This suggests that the mean scores of the Neuroticism Factor of Personality, within the broader context of the Big Five Factors of Personality, do not display a significant difference between male and female Teacher-trainees. In light of this evidence, the "null hypothesis" stating, "There is no significant difference in Neuroticism Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender," is not rejected. Consequently,

it can be concluded that male and female Teacher-trainees demonstrate an equal level of the Neuroticism Factor of Personality within the framework of the Big Five Factors of Personality.

Table 6 Comparison of Openness to Experience Factor of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	Result
Male	136	36.792	5.2244	.6157	1.918	Not Sig
Female	92	35.468	4.6606	.3731		

Table 6 shows the t- value for Gender is 1.918 which is not significant at .05 level. It means that mean score of Openness to Experience Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of male and female Teacher-trainees do not differ significantly. On basis of this "null hypothesis" "There is no significant difference in Openness to Experience Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality of Teacher-trainees in relation to Gender" is not rejected. It may be concluded that male and female Teacher-trainees had equal level of Openness to Experience Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality.

Discussion

Male and female Teacher-trainees exhibited an equal level of most Factors of Personality under the Big Five Factors of Personality, with the exception of Agreeableness and Conscientiousness. Specifically, female Teacher-trainees demonstrated a higher level of the Agreeableness Factor of Personality within the framework of the Big Five Factors compared to their male counterparts. This indicates a noteworthy gender-based influence on the development of the Agreeableness Factor of Personality among Teacher-trainees, highlighting the significant role that gender plays in shaping this particular aspect of personality. In the previous researches (Costa, Terracciano, & McCrae, 2001; Goodwin, & Gotlib, 2004; Chapman, Duberstein, & Lyness, 2007; Shokri, Kadivar, & Daneshvarpoor, 2007; Schmitt, Realo, Voracek, & Allik, 2008) while men scored higher on openness to experience (Goodwin, & Gotlib, 2004; Shokri, Kadivar, & Daneshvarpoor, 2007).

Male Teacher-trainees had higher level of Conscientiousness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality than female Teacher-trainees. It signifies males' higher inclination toward responsibility, organization, diligence, goal orientation, and adherence to established norms and rules than females. Contrarily Gender differences were discerned in relation to neuroticism, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness, with females consistently exhibiting higher scores than males for each trait (Rammstedt, & John, 2007).

The preceding literature findings underscore the alignment of a substantial number of studies with the present research, particularly concerning the Agreeableness factor of personality. However, it is noteworthy that a minority of studies present contradictory evidence. Consequently, the current study's alignment with a majority of previous research suggests a basis for researchers and educators to extrapolate gender bias tendencies in relation to the Agreeableness personality factor.

Agreeableness, characterized by traits such as cooperation, politeness, kindness, and friendliness, reflects a personality dimension where individuals with high scores tend to exhibit greater trust, affection, altruism, and prosocial behaviors. The findings of the present study indicate that girls in Physical Education possess these subtraits to a greater extent than boys in the same domain. This disparity holds implications for teachers and counsellors, suggesting the need to consider such information when guiding and providing opportunities for activities that demand these specific traits.

In juxtaposition to agreeableness, the examination of related literature reveals a relative scarcity of research on consciousness. This paucity emphasizes the need for further investigation to enhance our understanding and move towards generalizations about consciousness. While acknowledging the limitation of focusing on a specific population, the present findings emphasize the necessity of additional research to generalize the implications for consciousness, specifically within the current demographic.

Given the underexplored nature of literature on consciousness, it becomes imperative to conduct additional research. The current study's conclusion suggests a need for targeted interventions, such as training or education programs for girls in physical education, to foster the development of consciousness-related abilities. This nuanced approach recognizes the specific traits associated with consciousness and underscores the importance of tailored educational strategies to address these traits within the identified population.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Male and female Teacher-trainees had equal level of Extraversion Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality.
2. Female Teacher-trainees had higher level of Agreeableness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality than male Teacher-trainees.
3. Male Teacher-trainees had higher level of Conscientiousness Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality than female Teacher-trainees.
4. Male and female Teacher-trainees had equal level of Neuroticism Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality.

5. Male and female Teacher-trainees had equal level of Openness to Experience Factor of Personality under Big Five Factors of Personality.

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